

Constructivity, Computability, and Logic
A Collection of Papers in Honour of the 60th Birthday of
Douglas Bridges
J.UCS Special Issue

Cristian S. Calude

(Department of Computer Science, The University of Auckland, New Zealand
cristian@cs.auckland.ac.nz)

Hajime Ishihara

(School of Information Science Japan Advanced Institute of Science and Technology
Nomi, Ishikawa 923-1292, Japan
ishihara@jaist.ac.jp)

Professor Bridges is not only an eminent mathematician, but also a distinguished intellectual with many interests outside mathematics; music and sport are two of his other passions.

He has got a D.Sc. from Oxford University, and he is a Fellow of the Royal Society of New Zealand and a Corresponding Fellow of the Royal Society of Edinburgh.

His research interests are very broad and include constructive foundations of analysis and topology, mathematical economics, quantum logic and operator-theoretic foundations of physics, and theoretical computer science (computability and abstract complexity theory). Talking only numbers, Professor Bridges has published 116 papers in a selection of the best mathematics journals, and 12 papers in peer-refereed international conference proceedings.

Professor Bridges has written a number of very influential books: *Constructive Analysis* (with Errett Bishop), *Varieties of Constructive Mathematics* (with Fred Richman) and *Computability: A Mathematical Sketchbook* are among the best known and frequently cited. He and L.S. Viță have almost completed a book, *Techniques of Constructive Analysis*, which will be published by Springer Verlag in 2006 and which deals with many of the developments in constructive functional analysis over the past 20 years.

Many universities around the world have invited Professor Bridges to give talks in mathematics, physics, economics, and computer science. He was an invited speaker at the Brouwer Centenary Symposium (Netherlands, 1981), the meeting on *Truth in Mathematics* (Mussomeli, Sicily, 1995), and at various meetings of the network on Computability and Constructivity in Analysis.

Professor Bridges is extremely active in research: he has no less than eight papers accepted for publication in as many peer-refereed international journals. Currently he is engaged in several research projects, the most interesting being the foundations of topology (apartness spaces).

The papers published in this special issue of the *Journal of Universal Computer Science* (whose board of editors includes Professor Bridges) reflect the variety and depth of the research his work. All papers have been refereed according to J.UCS standard.

Finally we wish to thank all contributors to this special issue as well as Professor Hermann Maurer and Ms Dana Kaiser for their most valuable support. On behalf of all of us, from our hearts, "Happy Birthday, Douglas!".

Tabula Gratulatoria

Greetings and best wishes to Douglas S. Bridges
on the occasion of his 60th birthday from:

P. Aczel	S. Marcus	D. Ștefănescu
M. Baroni	H. Maurer	D. Streader
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